

numbering rice chromosomes and linkage groups. Cooperative coordinating committee members are M. E. Takahashi, chairman, Hokkaido Green-Bio Institute, East 5, North 15, Nagamuna, Hokkaido 068-13, Japan; K. J. Lampe, co-chairman, IRRI; G. S. Khush, secretary and editor, IRRI; H. I. Oka, editor, c/o National Institute of Genetics, Yata 1, 111 Mishima, Sizuoka-ken 411, Japan; Y. Futsuhara, secretary, Faculty of Agriculture, Nagoya University, Nagoya 464-01, Japan; D. Senadhira, treasurer, IRRI; T. Kinoshita, Plant Breeding Institute, Hokkaido University, Kita 9, Nishi 9, Sapporo 060, Japan; Min Shao-Kai, China National Rice Research Institute, Hangzhou, Zhejiang, China; G. Toennissen, The Rockefeller Foundation, 1133 Avenue of the Americas, New York, N.Y. 10036, USA; M. Jacquot, IRAT-CIRAD, BP 5035,34032 Montpellier Cedex, France; R. S. Paroda, ICAR, Krishi Bhawan, Dr. Rajendra Prasad Road, New Delhi 110 011, India; and M. H. Heu, College of Agriculture, Suweon, Korea.

The fourth annual meeting of the Rockefeller Foundation network on rice biotechnology preceded the symposium. ■

DTCP/UNDP training courses for 1991

The UNDP Asia and Pacific Programme for Development Training and Communication Planning (DTCP) provides a wide range of consultancy and training services to agriculture, forestry, health, family planning, and other rural development projects supported by the United Nations and other international aid agencies.

Regional training courses planned for 1991 include

- Communication planning 3-21 Jun
- Monitoring and evaluation of projects and programs 1-26 Jul
- Field- and middle-level management and supervision 5-30 Aug
- Planning and management of training programs 2-20 Sep
- Production and utilization of audio-visual materials 23 Sep - 1 Nov

- Training methods 4-23 Nov
- Brochures describing course content, methods, and participation are available from the Training Coordinator, DTCP/UNDP, cable UNDEVCOM Manila, FAX (632) 8 16-406 1, or write 5th Floor, Bonifacio Building University of Life Campus Meralco Avenue, Pasig, Metro Manila Philippines ■

INSURF Planning Meeting 11-14 Sep

The planning meeting of the International Network on Soil Fertility and Sustainable Rice Farming (INSURF) focused on subnetworks of INSURF working on key research areas (see table). Collaborating scientists from six countries and a representative of the Swiss Development Cooperation, INSURF's sponsoring agency, participated.

Following are some highlights of the meeting:

- The five existing subnetworks will continue, and satellite site work will be

INSURF research areas, lead centers, and satellite sites.

<i>Research area</i>	<i>Lead center (test sites)</i>
Genetic enhancement and integrated use of azolla in lowland rice-based farming systems	National Azolla Research and Training Center, China (India, Thailand, Pakistan, Philippines)
Green manure improvement and utilization for rice-based farming systems	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India (Thailand, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Philippines, Pakistan)
Soil fertility management for acid upland rice-based farming systems	Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (CRIFC & CSR), Indonesia, (Philippines, Madagascar, India, Thailand)
Soil fertility management for rice-based farming systems in infertile rainfed lowland soils	Department of Land Development, Thailand (Indonesia, India, Bangladesh)
Soil fertility management for lowland rice-based farming system, with emphasis on sulfur and other micronutrients	Philippine Rice Research Institute/University of the Philippines at Los Baños, (Pakistan, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Nigeria, India)
Soil fertility management for rice-based farming systems in favorable rainfed lowland soils	Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (CRIFC & CSR), Indonesia (Philippines, Bangladesh, India, Myanmar)

New IRRI publications

IRRI 1989 — planning for the 1990s

Crop loss assessment in rice

Seeds and seedlings of weeds in rice in South and Southeast Asia, by R. L.

strengthened. There will be greater ecosystem focus, in coordination with the ecosystem-based research programs at IRRI.

- The subnetwork on soil fertility management technologies for favorable rainfed lowland rice-based systems will start with the 1990-91 cropping seasons; the Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops at West Java, Indonesia, will be the lead center.

- A subnetwork on research issues of soil fertility management in direct-seeded rice has been proposed, in anticipation of trends toward more direct seeding of rice in some Southeast Asia countries. The Malaysian Agricultural and Research Development Institute (MARDI) would be the lead center.

- Mechanisms for closer interaction with ARFSN will be primarily in terms of joint training programs, information exchange, and perhaps common sites. Greater synergism and less duplication are the desired outcome of efforts toward closer interaction between INSURF and ARFSN. ■

Zimdahl, R. T. Lubigan, K. Moody, and M. O. Mabbayad

1990 supplement to publications of the international agricultural research and development centers ■